

Educational Leadership and Management as Catalyst for Academic Excellence in South West Nigeria's Colleges of Education

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Abstract

Original Research Article

The study investigated educational leadership and management as catalyst for academic excellence in south-west Nigeria's colleges of education. To achieve this two questions were raised and two hypotheses were formulated. Also descriptive-survey was adopted. The main population consisted of two hundred and five colleges of education in Nigeria out of it there are forty-seven in South-West Nigeria as at the time of this research, all academic staff, nonacademic staff, principal officers and students from both government and private colleges of education were the target. The sample of the study consisted of eight colleges of education, two each from four state, thirty-five staff each from the eight colleges of education making two hundred and eighty respondents, i.e 280 staff, using multi-stage, stratified and simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire

which consisted of 27 items and titled: Educational Leadership and management as catalyst for Academic Excellence in Colleges of Education, in South-West Nigeria. The questionnaire was personally administered on the respondents. Data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 23 and GMWV while hypothesis were tested at 5% level of significance and n-1 degree of freedom to students T-test. The study that: 88.89% of the sampled principal officers of the college of education were male, while 11.11% were female, 50% of the sampled principal officers of the colleges of education were private, while state owned and federal government colleges of education are 25% and 25% respectively. Staff responses on educational leadership

and management, impact on academic performance shows that frequent changes in course syllabus by NCCE affect quality of education in Nigeria were (MWV = 2.23), Provost of colleges of Education do not use autocratic but considerate (MWV = 2.87), the principal officers of the college are more united with both academic and non-academic staff for more effective management (MWV = 2.86), The nature of responsibilities and functions of leaders in colleges of education in south west are not significant.

There is no correlation between the nature of leadership style and management styles practices adopted in colleges of education in south west.

Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that: Frequent changes of course syllabus by NCCE should be discouraged; heads of department should be encourage to aspires for a highly responsive system and the student should be encourage to develop their personal talents and self-development.

If the aforementioned are surely taken care of, there will be a high management as well as administration and leadership competences and styles with corresponding high students' academic performance in the study area

Keywords: Academic performance, Administration, College of Education, Context, Impact, Leadership, Management, South-West, Teamwork.

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INTRODUCTION

Educational management and administration are processes used in school settings where managers persuade other members of the school organization to carry out the organization's strategies appropriately, on schedule, and with

the appropriate inputs. Adaptability is always improved by the correct inputs, which raises profitability, productivity, and quality (Taylor, 1991).

It is impossible to overstate the importance of high-quality education in Nigeria in the context of liberalization. Today's digital economy makes high-quality education more

important than ever. Nigeria is therefore forced to aim for that. Many issues are currently plaguing Nigeria's educational institutions. Ineffective school administration is frequently mentioned as a likely important contributing factor. Without a doubt, we require scientific management, as its tenets, when put into practice, have the potential to achieve maximum productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness (Osokoya, 2012).

Education is a vital tool for our development since it is the gateway to a developed society, and Nigeria is no exception. The knowledge and skills that students need to lead fulfilling lives are learned in school. Since the Federal Republic of Nigeria's National Policy of Education (1998:33) stressed that "no education system can raise above the quality of its' teachers," college administrators and heads of education play a significant role in overseeing and providing the desired leadership for achieving quality education. This suggests that the leadership of the Colleges of Education must be involved in order to provide high-quality education. For a while now, there has been discussion in the public sphere regarding how management affects the academic performance of the institution (Oandah, 2008).

Leadership, according to Akindele & Adepaju (2021), is the use of power and decision-making. These definitions essentially center on three elements: the authority's source, the task-relevantness of its application, and the authority's functions, which include decision-making, directing, and coordinating.

Everyone in our society is aware that education is essential to the overall growth of our country. It is anticipated that high-quality education will change society by influencing political climates and economic, social, and cultural endeavors. This is due to the fact that, if they are available, human resources play a crucial role in combining and activating material resources at the school level. Therefore, a lack of lecturers, a favorable learning environment, and a lack of human resources and learning materials are the main causes of the poor academic performance of education colleges.

According to this viewpoint, an organization is always a reflection of its manager or head of organization. According to Burns (1978), an organization's leadership strength directly correlates with both individual and organizational effectiveness. The ability of the management and administration team at work affects the academic performance of many educational institutions. According to Okumbe (2017), leadership in higher education plays a crucial role in influencing how instructors and students pursue academic achievement, extracurricular activities, and institutional goals.

Because of the aforementioned, the significance of leadership in colleges of education is greater now than it has ever been. Modern technology has resulted in a greater need for qualified and experienced individuals in management roles due to the growing importance and demand for high-quality educators and education.

Statement of the Problem

According to certain studies conducted in the region, management in Nigeria, especially in the South Western region of the country, directly affects the academic performance of

higher education institutions.

Finding the conditions under which management is likely to have an impact on academic performance in light of current challenges is more important in this context than merely copying the study to suit one's own interests.

The main question that the current study aimed to address was: Under what circumstances does effective and reliable management improve College of Education performance as indicated by NCCE results? In order to tackle this dilemma, one may choose to look at input and process variables both quantitatively and qualitatively when they are present, and consider their sufficiency or lack as problems that call for an innovative management solution. This is where the current research problem begins.

Purpose of the Study

This study aims to examine and evaluate the conditions under which management, administration, and leadership competencies and styles in Nigerian colleges of education sustainably facilitate and correlate with the academic performance level, given that management is one of the most significant factors in college education performance.

Significance of the Study

A study on educational leadership and management, impact on the academic performance of Colleges of Education in South-West Nigeria has the following significance.

Its goal is to produce data about how the management of the Colleges of Education contributes to improving academic achievement within their establishments.

Additionally, it would highlight the management difficulties Colleges of Education encounter and suggest some different approaches to address them in order to boost output.

Researchers who might want to look into the same topics can use the study's findings as a source of secondary data references.

Policymakers and other education stakeholders, including heads of colleges of education and NCCE, can also benefit from the study when reviewing educational policies.

Research Questions

In line with the purpose and relative significance of the study, the following question was adopted to guide the research:

- What is the nature of leadership style and management style in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria?
- What are the Responsibilities /Functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study.

Ho1. There is no correlation between the nature of the Responsibilities /Functions of leaders and the nature of leadership style and management style in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria?

Ho2. There is no correlation between the nature of

leadership styles and management styles and the style and the type of maintenance practices adopted in colleges of Education in South West Nigeria.

Leadership Theories

The field has benefited greatly from the contributions of leadership theories such as trait theory (e.g., Mann, 1959; Stogdill, 1948), contingency theory (e.g., Evans, 1970; Fiedler, 1967; Hersey & Blanchard, 1969; Vroom & Yetton, 1973), and transformational leadership theory (e.g., Bass, 1985). These theories all stress how crucial individual differences are to the leadership process.

Instructional Leadership

Instructional leadership is one type of leadership unique to educational environments. The idea first surfaced in the early 1980s when it was suggested that successful school principals prioritized academic, or instructional, leadership over administrative leadership. Prioritizing activities that advance students' learning is a sign of instructional leadership.

Clear goal-setting, curriculum management, teacher evaluation, lesson plan monitoring, and resource allocation for instruction are a few examples of these activities (Lashway, 2002). The principal prioritizes enhancing instruction and learning over handling paperwork. The idea has changed in recent years to focus on learning rather than teaching (Du Four, 2002), more advanced professional development, and decision-making based on data (King 2002).

In reality, achieving instructional leadership has proven challenging since it calls for redefining the principal's role and eliminating bureaucratic obstacles that are thought to stand in the way of leadership. Additionally, staff and administrative duties may be overlooked because the emphasis is on teaching and learning. Therefore, as a type of educational leadership, instructional leadership has not always been entirely effective.

Full Range Leadership

Developed from transformational leadership theory (e.g., Bass, 1985; Avolio et al., 1995), full range leadership (Avolio, 1999; Bass, 1999) has produced a significant amount of confirmatory research. People, timing, resources, interaction context, and the anticipated performance and motivational outcomes are the foundations of Avolio's (1999) framework for comprehensive leadership development. Three opposing leadership philosophies are distinguished by the full range leadership model (Avolio, 1999; Bass, 1999): transformational, transactional, and passive/avoidant.

Idealized traits, idealized actions, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and personalized attention are characteristics of transformational leadership (Bass, 1990a). In addition to inspiring followers with admiration, trust, and respect, leaders who display idealized traits and behaviors also set high ethical standards through their exceptional achievements (Bass, 1985). They are regarded as

gregarious, eloquent, perceptive, and motivating (Atwater, Penn, & Rucker, 1993).

Numerous favorable organizational outcomes, including improved job satisfaction, heightened commitment, heightened productivity, and lowered stress levels among followers, have been associated with transformational leadership (Northouse, 1997). By motivating followers to strive toward shared organizational objectives, transformational leadership may also positively impact organizational culture (Kickul & Neuman, 2000). Regardless of whether followers' opinions or organizational metrics are used to measure effectiveness, transformational leadership is thought to improve organizational effectiveness (Lowe et al., 1996).

General Views on Management

Using human resources to carry out organizational tasks and functions is the art of management. This art entails the use of public relations and human resources strategies, as well as the delegation of power through the assignment and sharing of tasks and responsibilities. According to Fayol (1949), it also entails communication, decision-making, problem-solving, and handling conflict and change.

Creating formal structures and establishing an organization based on a mission, goals, targets, functions, and tasks is the essence of management. Accordingly, schools are institutions that create unique management (Hoy and Miskel, 1996).

Management can be viewed as either an individual or a team. For instance, "The school management has changed the timetable in the middle of the semester," could be said by a lecturer or a student. This could be directed at the head of school alone, the entire principal staff of the college, or the members of the college's governing council or academic board. Similar to how a government has a cabinet of ministers, schools with multiple promoted employees may form a "senior management team" (Tatlah, Iqbal, Amin, Quraishi, 2014).

The study of management encompasses a wide range of subjects and topics. It is possible to gain management knowledge, abilities, and attitudes through education, experience, and various accredited courses. According to this viewpoint, management is a group of procedures that include action planning, problem solving, and decision making. These procedures entail the management of time, money, materials, and human resources. The functions of managers is another name for these procedures (Williams, 1993).

Effective Leadership, Administration and Management

Knowledge is never sufficient on its own. Effectively leading others requires more. Accepting the challenge of change is a necessary component of both effective management and effective leadership. Technology, education, creativity, freedom, the ability to make decisions for oneself, and self-awareness are all factors that contribute to change (Saad &

Khan, 2014).

Planning, organizing, coordinating, commanding, and controlling are the managerial functions, according to Saad & Khan (2014). Therefore, an effective manager wants everything to go according to the chain of command.

The rationale behind the management principles, according to Kooutz & O'donnell (1972), is to improve research for future theories and practice, increase efficiency, crystallize the nature of management, and achieve social goals in a particular system. Therefore, the application of management principles will be necessary for effective management.

Contributory Factors of Inadequate Access and Poor Quality of Colleges of Education in Nigeria

According to NPE (2013), the education system in Nigeria still faces many problems including, inter-alia, cross cutting issues.

- First, inadequate policy frameworks and statements which have negatively affected the development of quality of tertiary education.
- Second, existing law and regulations in education do not adequately address access and equity issues in education. Education Act of 2004 is referred to specifically on Universal Primary Education (UPE).
- Third, the curricula are over loaded, inappropriate and gender insensitive
- Fourth, the government's financial support to Colleges of Education, staff development and Education sector as a whole is inadequate.
- Fifth, policies and education structure to a large extent are still elitist and promote learning for examination oriented teaching and learning methods.
- Sixth, there is a high attrition of lecturer in the Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Many of these lecturers move to the private sector which pays them higher wages.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive-survey design was used in this investigation. On the other hand, a descriptive-survey design entails gathering information to test theories or provide answers regarding the present state of the variables in the research.

It ascertains and reports the current state of affairs. It makes an effort to characterize potential behaviors, attitudes, values, and traits.

Because it involves generalizing the results, the survey design method was therefore thought to be a suitable design that can be used to investigate Educational Leadership and Management: Impact on Academic Performances of Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria.

Population

The study's target populations include the 13,394 stakeholders that the NCCE identified, as well as the heads of

departments, academic and non-academic staff, students, and the provosts of the colleges of education.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sampling techniques used include multi-stage, stratified, and simple-random sampling techniques. The sampling was achieved in stages:

Stage I: The entire country was stratified into six region (i.e. North East, North West, North Central, South South, South East and South West). Out of these, South Western Nigeria was purposely selected.

Stage II: The selected region was thereafter stratified into the respective states such as, Ekiti, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo and Lagos States. Out of these, Ekiti State, Ondo State, Osun State and Oyo State were randomly sampled.

Stage III: Two Colleges of Educations were randomly selected from each of the sampled states for this study.

Stage IV: Thirty-five staff and forty students each were randomly selected from each of the sampled colleges of Education in each state. Altogether, a total of two hundred and eighty staff and three hundred and twenty students were sampled for this study.

Research Instrument

The instrument used to collect data for this study is a questionnaire titled, Educational Leadership and Management as Catalyst for Academic Excellence in Colleges of Education in South-West Nigeria". The questionnaire consists of three sections. Section A contains questions which sought after the personal information of the respondents and their schools. Section B contains questions on responsibility/ functions / leadership and management system Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Section C is on personal opinion / implementation of the College program.

Validity of the Instrument

Validity was the most critical criterion and indicated the degree to which an instrument measures what was supposed to measure. Also was thought of as utility, in other words validity was the extent to which differences found with a measuring instrument reflected true differences among those being tested. To ensure validity of the instrument, a draft copy of the questionnaire was prepared and submitted to my supervisor, for correction. A copy of the questionnaire was also shown to University lecturers in the field of Educational Measurement and Evaluation, for suggestions and comments. The final version of the questionnaire was created after considering their recommendations and remarks, and it was sent to the research supervisor for approval before the requested copies were made and distributed.

Reliability of the Instrument

Data reliability was taken as the cornerstone of making a successful and meaningful study. In order to collect reliable data, after the approval by the supervisor, copies of the

questionnaire were administered in six (6) colleges of education with similar settings but were not used for the study. After a period of two weeks, the same copies of this instrument were re-administered to the same respondents.

The data collected on the two occasions were collated and analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment reliability coefficient test to determine the reliability coefficient for this questionnaire. A reliable coefficient of 0.76 was obtained.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher visited the selected colleges of education and administered the specified copies of the structured questionnaire designed for this study to the respondents in each of the sampled Colleges of Education. Respondents were asked to indicate their answers in conformity to the pre-coded answers to information relating to their socio-economic status but indicate their responses on distribution of

leadership and management competencies, the challenges that school management face in a bid to improve the institution academic performance and the overall differential impacts of management on academic performance in the study area on 4-point Likert-scale with four options of “VT = Very True = 4 points, T = True = 3 points, U = Untrue =2 points and VU = Very Untrue =3 points.

DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS, AND DISCUSSIONS

Gender of the Respondents

The summary of the data collected on gender of the Principal Officers of Colleges of Education in the study area is as shown in Figure.1. Figure 1 shows that 88.89.0% of the sampled Principal Officers of the Colleges of Education are male while the remaining 11.110 % are females

Figure 1: Respondents Gender

Table 1: Table of Institution Nomenclature

Nomenclature	Frequency	Percentage
Federal	2	25.00
State	2	25.00
Private	4	50.00
Total	280	100

Table 1 shows the nature of Institution Nomenclature in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria. It was noted that 50% of the sampled Colleges of Education are Private

Colleges of Education while State owned and Federal Governments Colleges of Education are 25% and 25% respectively.

Table 2: Academic Qualification of Respondents

Qualification	Respondents	Percentage
PhD	89	31.79
M. Ed /M. Sc/M.A	125	44.64
B. Ed/B.A/B, Sc	53	18.92
DIP	7	2.50
Others	6	2.15

As shown in Table 2 about 31.79% of the respondents have Doctorate Degrees, 44.64% have either Masters' Degree (M.Ed /M.Sc/M.A) and, 18.92% have First Degree (B. Ed/B.A/B.Sc), In addition, another 2.5% have Diploma Certificates while the remaining 2.15% of the respondents are holders of other types

of Certificates.

Thus, 76.43% of the respondents have educational status that is above First Degree while 4.65 % are holders of certificates that are Non Degree.

Figure 2: Designations of Respondents

The designations of the respondents are as depicted in Figure 2. An examination of this figure showed that 95.35% of the respondents are academic staff while the remaining 4.65%

are nonacademic staff. Thus, majority of the respondents are academic staff.

Table 3: Respondents Post of Responsibility

Post	Respondents	Percentage
Senior Management	95	33.93
Middle Management	65	23.21
Junior Management	46	16.43
Non Management	74	26.43
Total	280	100

Table 3 depicted the summary of the data collected on post of responsibility of the respondents. From the table, 33.93% of the respondents are Senior Cadre Management staff while 23.21% of the respondents are Middle Cadre Management staff, Bur, 16.43% of the respondents are Junior

Cadre Management staff while the remaining 26.43% of the respondents are Non-Management staff.

Thus, 73.57% or a majority of the respondents are managerial staff while a minority of 26.43% are non-managerial staff.

Staff Responses on Educational Leadership and Management as Catalyst for Academic Excellence in Colleges of Education.

Table 4: Respondents Leadership Styles and Management Style

Statement Items	Responses					Likert Conversion					Mean Weight Value	Decision
	VT	T	U	V U	Total	4	3	2	1	Total		
A professional and qualified leadership promotes teaching and learning professionally as per college time-table.	84	75	65	56	280	336	225	130	56	747	2.67	A
The colleges of education heads, help lecturers to improve their teaching skills through motivation and encouragement	105	66	41	68	280	420	198	82	68	768	2.74	A
The heads of department helps their fellow staff to be well organized and well focused on the job	88	69	76	47	280	352	207	152	47	758	2.71	
Provost as a bureaucratic leader expect respect from followers as he/she is also a legally constituted authority	45	66	84	85	280	180	198	168	85	631	2.25	R
Provost of colleges of education do not like to be autocratic but considerate	118	56	58	48	280	472	168	116	48	804	2.87	A
The principal officers of the college encourage participatory leadership. style	56	75	83	66	280	224	225	166	66	681	2.43	R
The principal officers of the college are more united with both academic and non-academic staff for more effective ss in management.	115	61	53	51	280	460	183	106	51	800	2.86	A
Heads of department aspires for a highly responsive system of education that equips students with required knowledge, skills and positive attitudes	62	79	73	66	280	248	237	146	66	697	2.50	R
the college aspires for a highly responsive system of education that equips students with required knowledge, skills and positive attitudes	49	59	76	96	280	196	177	152	96	621	2.22	R
As a proactive provost of the college, whenever there is a value conflict, he/she shares it with the heads of department, management team and school board in general.	89	65	68	58	280	356	195	136	58	745	2.66	A
GMWV					0						2.59	

According to Table 4, the cut-off point or General Mean Weight Value (GMWV) for this analysis is 2.59. According to Sunmola (2017), as a rule factors whose Mean Weight Value (MWV) is lesser to the GMWV is rejected and vice-versa. Among the accepted nature of leadership and management style in colleges of education in the study area are

: provost of colleges of education do not like to be autocratic but considerate (MWV = 2.87) the principal officers of the college are more united with both academic and non-academic staff for more effective management (MWV =2.86), the colleges of education heads, help lecturers to improve their teaching skills through motivation and encouragement (MWV

= 2.74) the heads of department helps their fellow staff to be well organized and well focused on the job (MWV =2.71), a professional and qualified leadership promotes teaching and learning professionally as per college time-table (MWV = 2.67) and as a proactive provost of the college, whenever there is a value conflict, he/she shares it with the heads of department, management team and school board in general (MWV = 2.66).

Among the rejected nature of leadership and management style in colleges of education in the study area are: heads of department aspires for a highly responsive system of education that equips students with required knowledge, skills and positive attitudes (MWV = 2.50), the principal officers of the college encourage participatory leadership style (MWV = 2.43), Provost as a bureaucratic leader expect respect from

followers as he/she is also a legally constituted authority (MWV = 2.25) and the college aspires for a highly responsive system of education that equip students with required knowledge, skills and positive attitudes (MWV =2.22)

Text of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Ho1 The nature of the responsibilities / functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria are not significant.

The nature of the responsibilities / functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria are significant.

Table 5.: summary of X2 Analysis on the nature of the Responsibilities Functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria.

Variables	α	Df	Cal X ² Value	Tab X ² Value	Decision
The the nature of the Responsibilities /Functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria	0.05	(n-1) = (10-1) = 9	88.08	8.34	Reject H0

Ho1 The nature of the responsibilities /functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria are not significant.

The summary of data collected on the nature of the responsibilities /functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria (Table 4.) was subjected to Chi-Square Statistical analysis (Appendix II). The summary of the result of this analysis is as shown in Table5.

Table 5 indicates that at $p= 0.05$ and $df = 9$, the Calculated X2 value (88.08) is more than the Tabulated X2 value (8.34) hence, H0 is rejected. The foregoing signified that the nature of the responsibilities /functions of leaders in

Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria are significant.

Hypothesis 2

Ho2: There is no correlation between the nature of leadership style and management style and the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria.

There is no correlation between the nature of leadership style and management style and the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria.

Table 6: Summary of Correlation Analysis between the nature of leadership style and management style and the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria.

Variables	A	r	r ²	100 r ²
the nature of leadership style and management style and the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria.	0.05	0.78	0.6178	61.78%

The summary of the data collected on the nature of leadership style and management style in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria (Table 4) and the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria (Table 6) were subjected to Kendal Tau Statistical

Correlation Analysis. The summary of the result of this correlation analysis is as shown in Table 5.

Table 6 indicates that a positive moderate correlation (0.782) exists between the nature of leadership style and management style and the type of maintenance practices

adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria. This signifies that as the nature of leadership style and management style increases the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria also increases.

It is also noted that at $\alpha = 0.05$, a high variance of 0.7860 exists between the nature of leadership style and management style and the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria. Thus, the nature of leadership style and management style has 61.78% influence or variation on the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria while other related factors have the remaining 38.22% influence or variation on the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

It was observed that 88.89.0% of the sampled Principal Officers of the Colleges of Education are male while the remaining 11.110 % are females while 50% of the sampled Colleges of Education are Private Colleges of Education the State owned and Federal Governments Colleges of Education are 25% and 25% respectively. About 76.43% of the respondents have educational status that is above First Degree and a majority (95.35%) are academic staff among whom 73.57% are managerial staff.

It was also noted that there exists problem of teaching/learning resources (MWV = 2.71), due to the fact that Colleges of education established by the government were on politically motivated hence, poor administrative management (MWV = 2.71) cum shortage of resources materials in teaching and learning in the study area. This not only has implications on access and quality education but, also led to poor academic performance and poor quality of education in Colleges of Education in the study area.

It was also found out that Provost of colleges of education in the study area through motivation and encouragement, proactive, not autocratic but considerate (MWV =2.87) shares thoughts not only promotes teaching and learning professionally (MWV = 2.67) and with the heads of department, management team and school board in general (MWV = 2.66).

The foregoing managerial styles and skills have in deed helped lecturers to improve their teaching skills through (MWV = 2.74). In addition, the principal officers of colleges are more united with both academic and non-academic staff for more effective management (MWV =2.86). Moreover, aside that the Provosts of Colleges of education in the study area used the head of departments used to help their fellow staff to be well organized and well focused on the job (MWV =2.71), a professional and qualified leadership as per college time-table.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study revealed that the nature of the responsibilities / functions of leaders in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria are significant and thus, the nature of leadership style and management style increases

the type of maintenance practices adopted in Colleges of Education in South Western Nigeria.

Implication of Findings

The study's conclusions have ramifications; participants reported issues with teaching and learning materials, subpar academic achievement, unsatisfactory administrative oversight, frequent syllabus modifications by the NCCE, and communication flow in college administration. All of these factors have an impact on educational access and quality in Nigeria. Educational leadership at Nigerian institutions of education would unarguably undergo a negative shift and degenerate into off-purpose if the issue is not brutally resolved or addressed on a peripheral basis as soon as possible. The country as a whole will suffer greatly as a result, falling far short of sustainable development objectives and high-quality education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- Frequent changes of course syllabus by the NCCE should be discouraged as it affect the quality of education in colleges of education in Nigeria
- Heads of department should be encouraged to aspire for a highly responsive system of education that will equip students with required knowledge, skills and positive attitudes The school management should encourage students to develop their personal talents and self-development.
- School facility maintenance should be regarded as a vital component in the management of educational organization
- The colleges should maintain a safe and healthy learning environment for students and focus on student performance and care to improve the academic performance of the students.
- There will be high management, administration, and leadership competencies and styles, along with correspondingly good student academic achievement in the study field, if the aforementioned are irrefutably taken care of.

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